

LABOR INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PANDEMIC COVID19 ERA AND POST-PANDEMIC LABOR ISSUES

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Abstract

This paper highlights the problem of labor investment and its efficiency and the issue of labor problems in the post-covid-19 pandemic. The decline in labor investment is very bad in the tourism, aviation, and food industries. The phenomenon of the decline in investment in companies is divided into three, namely the company terminates employment, lays off workers for an indefinite period, and keeps workers and does not add them. A new trend in the labor market, namely remote working is having both positive and negative effects on the effectiveness of companies. This new job trend provides a widening gap between non-skilled and skilled workers, where companies will be more likely to use the services of outside workers because it can be done online. To overcome the gap of non-skilled workers who lack technological literacy, the government and various stakeholders, along with industry, must create a skill improvement program, so as to reduce the gap between non-skilled workers and active educated unemployed, which can be gradually overcome in the post-pandemic period.

Keywords: labor investment, efficiency, post-covid-19 pandemic.

JEL Codes: F16, J08

1. Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has become a worldwide epidemic since 2019 and even now. This epidemic has shifted all the orders of life that are commonly carried out, including the industrial world, which absorbs a lot of workers in Indonesia. The Head of the Indonesian Investment Coordinating Board (BKPM), revealed that the Covid-19 outbreak had a significant impact on investment realization and employment (Machmudi, 2020).

The Institute for Development of Economics and Finance (INDEF) predicts that there is a potential loss of investment value of IDR 127 trillion due to the outbreak of COVID-19. This is not without reason, considering that one of the contributing factors is the prospect of economic activity and growth which is increasingly depressed. The Indonesian Minister of Manpower, explained that one of the industrial targets that have been most affected by COVID-19 is the tourism sector. This was mainly due to the policies of Indonesia and other countries that closed airport access from international flights which caused the number of tourist visits to Indonesia to plummet. The Central Statistics Agency noted that there was a decrease of 7.62% in foreign tourist arrivals in January 2020, the period when COVID-19

began to spread in the world. As a result, many hotel owners in Bali and Batam have been forced to lay off their employees (BKPM, 2020).

Total foreign tourist visits to Indonesia in 2020 amounted to 4.02 million visits. When compared to 2019, the number of foreign tourists decreased by 75.03 percent. Based on nationality, there are 5 countries that visited Indonesia the most in 2020, namely Timor Leste, Malaysia, Singapore, Australia, and China. Most of these countries are neighboring countries, except for China. This significant decline in the number of tourists has a very significant impact on economic conditions because tourism plays an important role in increasing state income, foreign exchange, and employment. The pandemic threatens 13 million workers in the tourism sector and 32.5 million workers who are indirectly linked to the tourism sector (Central Board Statistic (BPS) (2021).

Figure1. Development of Indonesian Foreign Tourist Visits

The Covid-19 pandemic has impacted productivity with challenges to the labor market and education, as well as to investment and the private sector, especially in the transportation and tourism sectors. In this regard, the Governor of Bank Indonesia, Perry Warjiyo, emphasized the importance of the G20's role through pro-productivity policies, investment, strengthening the labor market and capital relocation (Bank of Indonesia, 2022).

The Indonesian government has designated Covid-19 as a National Disaster according to Presidential Decree No. 12/2020 concerning the Determination of Non-Natural Disasters for the Spread of Covid-19 as a National Disaster, the government has gradually asked the public to reduce activities outside the home through physical distancing policies, regional quarantines to Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) followed by the implementation of learning and working from home. The enactment of these policies has an impact on

the economic sector, especially the sustainability of jobs and income. To find out the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on employment, the Indonesian Institute of Sciences (LIPI), the Manpower Research and Development Agency of the Ministry of Manpower and the Demographic Institute of the Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Indonesia conducted an online survey. The survey was conducted during the period from 24 April to 2 May 2020 for the population aged 15 years and over, with a total of 2,160 respondents who were recruited spread across 34 provinces in Indonesia, indicating that there was a decrease in the use of labor in 36% of those who terminated their employment, and 50% lay off employees without layoffs.

Figure 2. The Impact of Covid 19 on Reduction of Workers in Companies

The graph above shows that 50% of companies reduce their workforce by termination of employment, and 36% are able to survive without termination, but also do not increase investment in labor. On the other hand, the COVID-19 pandemic is forcing all parties to leave the old ways and switch to new habits or often called the new normal. The impact on the world of work is the application of working from home or Work From Home (WFH) or Flexible Working Space (FWS) where work can be carried out from home via WFH or from co-working space available at the company's satellite office. The implementation of FWS results in both positive and negative impacts, but if viewed from the point of view of budget efficiency, FWS policies that are implemented effectively will contribute in the form of savings in operational costs (Firzada, 2021) and whether this work method can still be an effective method in the post-pandemic period or not, This still needs to be studied.

2. Literature Review

Labor Investment efficiency

The efficiency of labor investment is defined as the optimal rate of hiring (maximizing value) employees (Firzada, 2021). Another literature is that labor investment efficiency is defined as the difference between the actual employment growth rate and the expected employment growth rate. An efficient investment is made when a firm chooses an investment that brings about a positive net present value in the absence of market friction (Benmelech, 2011 & Hyumin, 2022). Asymmetric information causes market friction that affects the hiring or firing of workers in companies. The explanation for inefficient labor investment is the

presence of an organized or strong workforce in unions, making layoffs more expensive and with inherent wages. This causes management to maintain the information asymmetry of trade unions and work boards because sharing information can increase the bargaining power of trade unions or work boards. Empirical studies find that investment in an efficient workforce is important because it is positively related to the long-term success of the firm (Lopatta et al., 2019).

Labor Use Efficiency

Labor management strategies and technological innovations that improve labor productivity and efficiency may play an important role in adaptation to tightening labor markets and rising labor costs. Company managers may choose to hire professionally skilled workers to increase labor productivity, or invest capital in equipment and technology to replace labor inputs (Jing, 2019).

Covid-19 Mitigating Measures and Programs and Labor Market Adjustments

COVID-19 has forced governments to inflict economic pain on their own to slow infection rates and save lives. Measures taken by governments to deal with pandemics vary between countries, within countries and over time, depending on the risk of infection with the virus, the strengths and weaknesses of the healthcare system; fiscal capacity to provide financial support to individuals and businesses; and implicit judgments of human life. Strict economic measures, such as confinement, have had very heterogeneous direct and indirect effects. The mandated office closure policies and operational restrictions had a drastic effect on the uncertainty of labor demand by non-essential businesses. The indirect impact through variations in unemployment and employment causes a significant reduction in consumption, which in turn will change the fortunes of food producers. Some have benefited from strict lockdowns while others have experienced sudden drastic reductions in demand. The effects of the pandemic on labor demand varied across sectors, but this was mainly conditioned by the stringency of measures adopted or stopped by governments. Strict mitigation measures are in line with unemployment in various countries, but lockdowns and the imposition of curfews are not necessarily the main factors that condition unemployment in a country. Countries that choose to adopt some mitigation measures to limit economic woes still have to contend with falling world demand for all goods.

It is easy to criticize policy responses made by one country and another, but policymakers are under tremendous pressure and have little information to adapt current policies and programs quickly and to design and implement new ones. Scientific information on COVID-19 is unclear as of early 2020. Testing and tracing capacity is limited and all governments around the world are in dire need of medical supplies. Regulations should be developed urgently for all workplaces as well as financial incentives to make businesses and workers comply with large-scale activity restrictions. Obtaining incentive entitlements is not easy, especially when policies have to be made. Governments must decide between protecting jobs or protecting workers, or doing a bit of both (Yulisfan et al., 2021).

3. Methods

The research method used is a systematic literature study. A systematic review is carried out with the stages of labor and efficiency issues that occur during the pandemic and after the pandemic. The indicators of the developed literature review are:

- a. Review of labor investment problems and their efficiency during the pandemic
- b. The issue of labor problems in the post-pandemic

4. Result and Discussion

4.1. Result

Labor Investment Efficiency in Pandemic Covid19

Based on the results of the literature study that has been carried out, during the Covid-19 pandemic there was a decrease in labor investment and an increase in unemployment. In Canada, for example, it was noted that unemployment rose rapidly in the spring of 2020 as a result of stringent public health protection measures. Low-wage workers have been particularly hard hit, including restaurant workers. Other workers in the agri-food sector have been less affected by public health measures and the pandemic. During the prolonged Covid-19 Pandemic it will affect the labor market, with the unemployment rate rising so fast almost all over the world.

The COVID-19 pandemic has not only affected the labor market in Romania but has also affected the mentality of employees, and the macroeconomic level. The COVID-19 pandemic has led to an increase in the number of unemployed in the Romanian labor market. In conclusion, we can say that changes in the labor market have been and will be directly affected by the development of the pandemic situation. Uncertainty about information regarding the end of this pandemic will greatly affect investment and labor efficiency.

Environmental factors represent a crisis, leading to levels of innovation, namely radical and incremental, and can be approached using a customized adaptive consolidation process (Tambunan et al., 2018). There are four strategic options from Miles and Snow in identifying and responding to crises; namely (1) exploitative-defender innovation; (2) analyzer-organization ambidexterity; (3) explorer-miner innovation and (4) reactor-leave or close business (Larue, 2021).

Firm labor investment is negatively correlated with economic policy uncertainty. And the efficiency of firms' labor investment (and overinvestment in labor) is positively (negatively) correlated with economic policy uncertainty, which is more significant for non-SOEs and firms with less government intervention (Khaddafi et al., 2018). Furthermore, the positive relationship between economic policy uncertainty and labor investment efficiency is more significant for labor-intensive firms, firms in competitive industries, firms in advanced labor markets and firms under strong labor law protections. In addition, the uncertainty of economic policies encourages companies to make adjustments to their human capital

structure and allocate more employees with high human capital, which ultimately helps companies achieve higher total factor productivity (Lukito-Budi et al , 2022).

Social implications

The government needs to consider the impact of economic policies on enterprises when introducing and changing policies and guide enterprises to increase human capital allocation under different internal and external conditions to finally realize the optimal allocation of social resources (Heikal et al., 2018).

Post-Pandemic Labor Issues

The recession impact of the pandemic resulted in a loss of economic and social fabric, and it could take years to catch up with pre-pandemic growth. Fortunately, recovery is expected to be quick. Unemployment will decline and should continue to fall as curfews and temporary business closures are lifted, but not all is well. Workers who were laid off before the pandemic and who have been unemployed for a year or more will face greater challenges than workers who have just been laid off in finding work. They are more likely to stay in lower paying jobs that will lower their lifetime income and to experience health problems that will lower their life expectancy (Chu, J., & Fang, 2020).

The practice of remote work has been widely adopted and is part of a new trend in companies especially in Educational Institutions. Continuous remote work has been reported to reduce productivity, but if it is done 2-3 days a week it can increase productivity and be enjoyable for workers. With the increase in broadband services, far beyond densely populated urban areas, some workers have decided to move to the countryside (von Wachter, 2020). Time will tell whether this employment trend will persist or be temporary.

Besides the adoption of new ways of working, challenges also occur for low-skilled workers. The result in the international trade literature is that outsourcing/offshoring of tasks increases the wage gap between skilled and unskilled workers in rich and poor countries. Delegating work overseas is made easier with Zoom, Teams, Adobe, and Skype becoming ubiquitous tools and this raises concerns about inequality. Past pandemics have lowered job prospects among poorer workers and increased the gap between upper and lower incomes. The most pressing challenge in terms of the agricultural workforce remains the recruitment and retention of agricultural workers. COVID-19 is bringing more attention to this issue in Canada and in other industrialized countries (Bloom, 2020).

The reskilling process must be programs that really need to be carried out, which involve various stakeholders, and are right on target. The first stage should involve the identification of sectors for intervention to facilitate the establishment of institutions that will specifically have the task of linking workers to the needs of the post-pandemic industry, mediated by the acquisition of new skills in the identified educational institutions. This should be followed by identifying jobs in the economy that require skills that require a short period of time to have skills in internet marketing, animation, video content creation and editing, ad creation, and others. The next phase should include the identification of institutions and vocational

academies that offer courses and programs and are equipped with the capacity to teach skills in short course formats, but are also willing to modify their curricula to suit employer requirements, worker demographics, and competencies and changing job requirements.

To increase industry and stakeholder participation, program financing should be borne as much as possible by central government, local governments, employee associations and other voluntary contributions from the business community, and international development agencies (ILO, UNDP, World Bank, UNIDO, and ADB, among others). Such a format will increase the willingness of both employers and employees to participate in the program. A good example of a successful retraining program is the Virginia Ready Initiative in the state of Virginia. The program is able to retrain laid-off workers through a program that connects laid-off workers, Virginia colleges (education and training providers), employers, and the Virginia government talent pool empowerment program.

However, in the long term, there is a need to address the growing and growing problem of educated unemployment in Indonesia. While the unemployment rate defined as the percentage of the labor force actively seeking work but unable to find it has declined and is projected to remain at most at 5% by 2022. Unemployment was 1.49% in 2014, rising to 4.58 (2016), 3 .04 (2017), 5.28 (August 2019), and is projected to remain around 5% over the 2018–2023 period (IMF, 2018) (Larue, 2021).

Figure 3. The Unemployment Rates

While addressing the underlying problems facing workers lies in large part in reforming the education system, we believe that some steps the government should take should specifically focus on improving the dynamics of the labor market as it is today. Even before the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, labor relations in Indonesia were far from friendly. One area that has been a constant source of tension between employees, on the one hand, and employers and the government, on the other, relates to the drafting and implementation of a job creation

law (UU No.11/2020). The law claims to remove a number of rules and procedures that have created barriers and uncertainty for employers in hiring and firing employees when and when conditions permit; difficulties in obtaining operational permits.¹⁶ Other contentions include government regulations that index annual wage increases against inflation, which eliminates the need for lengthy annual negotiations between employers, trade unions, and local government, and outsourcing. These conditions have created uncertainty for entrepreneurs, including FDI companies, forcing them to relocate their production facilities to other countries. Some of the recent cases include, among others, NISSAN, Chevrolet, and SAMSUNG electronics (Ssenyonga, 2021).

4.2. Discussion

This paper highlights the problem of labor investment and its efficiency and the issue of labor problems in the post-pandemic period. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a very bad impact on the decline in labor investment in the tourism, aviation and food industries. The phenomenon of the decline in investment in companies is divided into three, namely the company terminates employment, lays off workers for an indefinite period, and keeps workers and does not add them. During the pandemic corporate governance in companies as a lever to reduce information asymmetry and try information asymmetry and agency theory in relation to the impact of information asymmetry on investment efficiency. This also confirms the theory which states that corporate governance can be considered as a determinant of investment efficiency. Uncertainty about COVID-19 information will have an impact on difficult economic policies for the government which tends to give investors doubt, companies actively reduce labor demand and increase labor investment efficiency by optimizing the allocation of human capital.

The COVID-19 pandemic has introduced a new trend in the labor market, namely the adoption of faster technology, ways of working remotely that have both positive and negative effects on company effectiveness. This new job trend provides a widening gap between non-skilled and skilled workers, where companies will be more likely to use the services of outside workers because it can be done online. The government must carry out a reskilling program that involves various stakeholders, so that it is right on target. Identification of sectors for intervention to facilitate the establishment of institutions that will specifically have the task of linking workers to post-pandemic industrial needs, mediated by the acquisition of new skills in identified educational institutions. The government must cooperate with the Workers' Association, International Institutions in financing this program so that the participation of workers and employers will be maximized. If this program is successful, then the problem of rapid adoption of new technology and educated unemployment in the active workforce, especially in Indonesia, will be resolved, so that it is decreasing every year.

5. Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has had a very bad impact on the decline in labor investment in the tourism, aviation, and food industries, where they tend to make companies lay off employment, lay off workers for an indefinite period, but also retain workers and not add

them. Economic policies during difficult times during the Covid-19 Pandemic for the government had an impact of doubt on investors; companies actively reduced labor demand and increased labor investment efficiency by optimizing the allocation of human capital. New trends in the labor market, namely the adoption of faster technology, ways of working that can be done remotely if done permanently will reduce effectiveness, but if done hybrid can increase work effectiveness. To overcome the gap of non-skilled workers who lack technological literacy, the government and various stakeholders, along with industry, must make a skill improvement program, so that the gap between non-skilled workers and educated active unemployment can be gradually overcome.

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